

Understanding E-Scooter Route Choice Behavior in Washington DC Using a Computer Vision Enriched Dataset

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Abstract

E-scooters have emerged as a popular mode of travel, offering a flexible and low-emission alternative for short urban trips. To support effective infrastructure design and improve user experience, it is critical to understand how riders choose their routes. This study models e-scooter route choice behavior in Washington, DC using a large-scale, high-resolution GPS trajectory dataset. It advances previous work by applying route choice modeling to a complex urban setting and by incorporating novel predictors, i.e., streetscape features extracted from Google Street View imagery through computer vision, which captures context-specific environmental factors that influence user preferences. The main technical steps involve converting GPS trajectories into polyline trip routes using Fast-Map-Matching (FMM), generating choice sets using the Breadth-First Search Link Elimination (BFSLE) method, and modeling route choices with the Path Size Logit (PSL) model. We find that protected bicycle facilities are critical for attracting e-scooter use on major roads with higher speeds and traffic volumes, whereas the difference between protected and painted lanes is less pronounced on minor roads. We have also identified a tendency toward sidewalk riding among e-scooter users, raising concerns about pedestrian safety and regulatory compliance. These results suggest a need for cities to prioritize fully protected lanes on high-traffic corridors. Overall, e-scooter route preferences largely align with those of cyclists, but with key differences: e-scooter users are more flexible, more tolerant of moderate slopes, and less sensitive to traffic signals. In other words, e-scooter riders place greater emphasis on directness and continuity in their route choices. In addition, our study highlights the complementary role of streetscape features (trees, sky visibility and building facades) in promoting e-scooter riding. Notably, our findings suggest that to encourage micromobility use, cities should prioritize expanding tree canopy for summer shade and enhancing urban design elements that create a balance of openness and enclosure.

Keywords: E-scooter, Micromobility, Infrastructure, Route Choice, Path Size Logit

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1. Introduction

In recent years, e-scooters have surged in popularity, becoming the most widely used micromobility option in urban areas. As the rapid growth of e-scooter carries significant implications for road infrastructure, understanding the dynamics of e-scooter travel, particularly route choice behavior, is an increasingly important research topic. Improved knowledge of e-scooter route choice behavior can aid in designing safer and more efficient urban infrastructure. For example, if planners understand which routes are preferred by e-scooter users, they can prioritize the development of dedicated lanes and pathways that minimize conflicts with vehicles and pedestrians, thereby enhancing safety for all road users. Insights into route preferences can also inform the placement of docking stations and charging facilities, ensuring they are conveniently located to meet user demand. Moreover, understanding e-scooter route choice behavior supports environmental sustainability goals. By promoting e-scooter usage on routes that minimize travel distance and time, cities can reduce overall emissions and energy consumption. This aligns with broader efforts to create sustainable and resilient urban environments.

While the topic of bicycle route choice has been well studied, e-scooters have some unique characteristics that differ from traditional bicycles. Notably, factors such as greater agility, different accessibility options, and unique rider preferences introduce nuanced differences between e-scooter and bicycle travel. These differences suggest that much of the existing knowledge regarding bicycle route choice is not applicable to e-scooters, highlighting the need to consider the specific characteristics of e-scooter trips and distinct preferences of e-scooter users when modeling their route choice behavior. In other words, the current bicycle route choice modeling pipeline must be adapted, such as making changes to data processing, parameter settings, and model specification to accommodate the distinct characteristics of e-scooter users.

To enrich the empirical evidence on micromobility route choice and inform infrastructure planning in an era of growing e-scooter use, this study investigates the factors influencing e-scooter route choice behavior in Washington DC, where thousands of shared e-scooters have been deployed across the region since 2017. Leveraging shared e-scooter trip trajectory data collected from public APIs, we developed a path size logit model to uncover the underlying factors that influence e-scooter riders' route preferences. To our knowledge, this is the first study to use GPS-based trip trajectory data and discrete choice model methods to explore the factors influencing e-scooter route choices in a large and diverse urban context. Moreover, leveraging recent advances in computer vision, this study incorporates streetscape features extracted from Google Street View (GSV) imagery. These data complement traditional GIS sources (e.g., OpenStreetMap or government open data) by capturing streetscape elements that are often overlooked but relevant to route preferences of micromobility users. The incorporation of these variables results in more behaviorally meaningful route choice models and generates new empirical evidence on the role of streetscape features in shaping micromobility routing behavior. In sum, the specific research objective of this study is to examine how various road environment attributes, including GSV-derived streetscape features, shape e-scooter users' route choices in an urban environment.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 reviews the literature on route choice modeling and factors shaping micromobility travel behavior. Section 3 describes the dataset and outlines the procedures for data preparation and processing. Section 4 introduces the model specification and variables of interest. Section 5 presents the estimation results and the Value of Distance (VoD) analysis. Section 6 discusses policy implications and highlights similarities and differences between e-scooter and bicycle route choice behavior. Finally, Section 7 concludes.

2. Literature Review

Route choice is an individual process within the trip assignment phase of the classic four-step travel demand model. Route choice modeling plays a pivotal role in understanding the decision-making process of travelers within urban environments. The following subsections will introduce the modeling techniques and summarize the factors affecting route choice for micromobility as found in the literature.

2.1. Route choice modeling approaches

Various techniques have been employed to analyze and predict route preferences. Discrete choice models are most commonly used for route choice modeling, which are derived from the random utility maximization framework. Typically, discrete choice models based on revealed preference data are used. Specifically, the methodology involves extracting individual trips from observed data (such as GPS data), map-matching these trips to an appropriate road network, generating a choice set based on the network, calculating road-related features of interest, and finally selecting and designing the model structure. In the literature, two main statistical approaches have been widely explored and implemented: route-based (or path-based) methods and link-based methods.

Route-based methods are the most common in route choice modeling. These models estimate parameters by comparing observed routes with non-chosen alternatives, each characterized by attributes such as distance, number of junctions, and scenery. Random utility models describe individual choice behavior by assigning a utility to each alternative, composed of observed and random components. The Multinomial Logit (MNL) model is a common example but assumes independence among alternatives. To address this, correction models adjust the utility to capture correlations between similar choices. The most prevalent type is the Multinomial-correction model, which adds a correction term to the utility function to account for correlation effects. A typical example is the Path Size Logit (PSL) model, which has a long theoretical history. This model extends the Multinomial Logit by including a Path Size factor in the utility function, penalizing overlapping routes within the choice set (i.e., trips sharing one or more segments). PSL has been widely used to handle route choice problems (Marra and Corman, 2020; Meister et al., 2023; Nielsen et al., 2021; Sevtsuk et al., 2021; Ton et al., 2018; Yap and Cats, 2021).

This PSL approach depends on generating a choice set that includes unchosen alternatives, which itself is a distinct research area. Most choice set generation methods are deterministic, involving repeated shortest path searches within the network. Prato and Bekhor (2006)

introduces the Branch and Bound method, which constructs paths based on specific conditions such as direction, time, similarity, loops, and movements (e.g., avoiding left turns). For example, temporal constraints ensure a route is included only if its travel time does not exceed the shortest time by a certain factor. Rieser-Schüssler et al. (2013) developed the Breadth First Search Link Elimination (BFSLE) method. BFSLE first calculates the least cost path from origin to destination, then eliminates links in order to find a new shortest path. The most used measure to evaluate the quality of choice sets is the ability to reproduce the observed behavior. Ton et al. (2018) identifies BFSLE as the most effective method for generating a choice set. Consequently, the combination of BFSLE and Path Size Logit (PSL) has become the most common route-based method in recent years.

2.2. Factors influencing route choice of micromobility

Since e-scooters and bicycles share many operational and spatial characteristics, and research on bicycle route choice is far more extensive, it is helpful to synthesize findings from the cycling literature to inform e-scooter route choice modeling. The well-established body of work on bicycle route choice offers valuable insights into environmental and infrastructural preferences that likely translate to e-scooter users. For instance, Meister et al. (2024) summarized that cyclists generally prefer shorter routes with dedicated cycling infrastructure and scenic environments, while avoiding routes with steep gradients, mixed traffic (including motorized and pedestrian), traffic signals, and complex intersections. Similarly, Lukawska et al. (2023) found that cyclists favor protected infrastructure and green or water-side environments, with route preferences differing by cyclist type and trip length—especially for infrequent riders and long-distance trips. Meister et al. (2023) further highlighted that route choice is shaped by infrastructure quality, socio-demographic characteristics, and bicycle type; for example, e-bicycle users are more tolerant of steep slopes and higher speeds, emphasizing the need for differentiated infrastructure such as cycling highways. In addition, ? provided fine-grained estimates of cyclists’ generalized cost across different infrastructure types, showing that protected bike lanes—particularly on major roads—substantially reduce perceived cost, and that cycleways in green or industrial areas are especially attractive due to their separation from traffic. Their findings underscore the importance of detailed, link-level infrastructure representation in capturing cyclists’ preferences and the induced demand effects of bicycle-friendly design.

While e-scooters share some similarities with bicycles as a form of micromobility, they also present distinct characteristics and challenges. Unlike bicycles, e-scooters offer greater agility and accessibility, and they attract a different user demographic, typically younger and higher-income individuals (Badia and Jenelius, 2023). E-scooters also serve shorter trips, with mean distances ranging from 1 to 4.7 km and durations between 7.6 and 20 minutes (Badia and Jenelius, 2023). The nature of e-scooter mobility differs significantly, often influenced by trip purposes, pricing policies, and temporal patterns. E-scooter trips are usually concentrated in city centers and other densely populated areas with significant commercial and recreational activities. Factors such as street connectivity, bicycle lane coverage, availability of docking stations, and limited car parking space also contribute to spatial travel behavior (Huo et al., 2021).

There is a limited number of studies that conduct e-scooter route choice modeling. Zhang et al. (2021) conducted a pioneer study using e-scooter trip data collected from a university campus. They found that cycleways have the largest positive estimated coefficients, making them the most preferred infrastructure for e-scooter users. Conversely, stairs on walkways are highly unattractive, with users willing to travel 55% longer to avoid them. E-scooter riders favor infrastructure separated from cars, such as bike lanes and mixed-use trails. While their model provides valuable insights into e-scooter users' preferences for different transportation infrastructures, their research is confined to a university campus context. This may not fully represent the conditions and challenges of urban road environments.

Our study extends the work of Zhang et al. (2021) to examine the urban environment of Washington DC, providing a broader context for understanding e-scooter route choice. By including a variety of urban settings, our findings can offer more comprehensive insights into the preferences and behaviors of e-scooter users in diverse city landscapes. This broader scope provides generalized evidence for factors influencing e-scooter route choice, thereby contributing to more effective transportation planning and infrastructure design.

3. Data

3.1. *The GBFS and e-scooter trip trajectory data*

Washington DC was an early adopter of shared e-scooters, permitting seven operators, including Bird, Jump, Lime, Lyft, Razor, Skip, and Spin, to offer service beginning in 2017. The District Department of Transportation (DDOT) established operational requirements, including a mandate that vendors provide publicly accessible data through Application Programming Interfaces (APIs). These APIs deliver data in the General bicycleshare Feed Specification (GBFS) format, a widely adopted open data standard for micromobility systems. GBFS data includes details such as vehicle ID, latitude and longitude, reservation and disabled status, and battery level. We developed a Python script to scrape GBFS data at one-minute intervals, although actual update frequencies vary by vendor (from one to ten minutes). The GBFS data recorded the GPS locations of shared e-scooters in the city over time. Because the GBFS data obtained from other vendors do not allow us to infer e-scooter trip trajectories or due to data quality issues, we decided to only keep Lime's data for the period of February 21, 2019 to July 18, 2019 for route choice modeling, resulting in 125 consecutive days of observation.

Each entry in the dataset represents a GPS point, including latitude, longitude, a second-level timestamp, and a unique e-scooter ID that remains stable over time. This consistent ID allows us to accurately infer e-scooter trips and reconstruct the trip trajectories. In processing the data, we identified and removed periods during which a scooter repeatedly reported the same GPS coordinates at one-minute intervals over extended durations (e.g., one hour), indicating that the vehicle was stationary. These points do not reflect actual movement and may result from idling, GPS drift, or users' failure to end a trip.

We then constructed trip trajectories by applying two criteria: (1) sequences of points must share the same ID and be sampled continuously, and (2) a gap of more than two minutes between consecutive points of the same ID was used to define trip start and end points. We

then refined the trip data by excluding trips shorter than 2 minutes, longer than 90 minutes, with speeds outside 2–15 mph, or distances outside 0.4–3 miles. Additionally, we excluded all e-scooter trips near the DC National Park area, as such trips are likely recreational and may not reflect purposeful route choices, making them less suitable for modeling. After processing, 48,141 valid trips were identified for this study (Figure 1), which incorporate all trip trajectories in DC.

Figure 1: Lime E-scooter Trips from February 21, 2019 to July 18, 2019

3.2. Data processing steps for route choice modeling

This section outlines the methodological framework used to prepare the input data for modeling e-scooter route choice behavior. It includes three key steps: (1) preparing the road network and applying a map matching algorithm to align raw GPS trajectories with the transport infrastructure; (2) cleaning and refining matched trajectories to ensure valid

origin–destination (OD) pairs; and (3) filtering trips based on the availability of street-level built and natural environment data. These steps ensure that the input data are spatially accurate and behaviorally meaningful for subsequent choice set generation and model estimation.

3.2.1. Network and map matching

Map matching is a crucial step that assigns GPS-based trajectories to a series of links or nodes (and related network attributes) to precisely reconstruct users’ actual paths. As reviewed in a recent study by Berjisian and Bigazzi (2023), map matching for active travel modes is more complex than for car travel, highlighting two main challenges: 1) Cyclists and pedestrians do not always stick to official roads and paths, sometimes opting for shortcuts that may be missing from the network. 2) The types of infrastructure these users are allowed to use, and actually do use, are not always clearly defined. Individuals often switch between closely parallel facilities that traditional matching algorithms struggle to detect. For e-scooters, these challenges are even more pronounced. E-scooter users have more flexible path choices, and their right of way on different road types is often intertwined and ambiguous.

We utilized Fast Map Matching (FMM) to process the trip trajectories, requiring not only the trajectory data but also the road network data (Yang and Gidofalvi, 2018). OpenStreetMap (OSM) provides road network data compatible with FMM’s input requirements. The optional network levels as the FMM input include driving, biking, and walking. Considering the ordinances on e-scooter road use in DC, scooters are permitted to use all designated bike lanes, are forbidden from riding on sidewalks in the central business district, and are encouraged to avoid sidewalks in pedestrian-heavy areas. Therefore, in practice, e-scooters are likely to use both bike lanes and sidewalks, depending on the specific location and context. Given that OSM’s walk-level network covers most of the bicycle-level network, we opted to use the walk-level network. This choice could introduce some inaccuracies, such as when an E-scooter actually travels on a link that is not represented in the walk-level network. However, such cases are very rare (5%), and the resulting inaccuracies are considered acceptable. Conversely, using the less complicated bicycle-level network could have matched a significant portion of trips taken on sidewalks to bike lanes with significant offsets, creating a much larger error. Another potential issue with such approach is that some segments with parallel bike paths and sidewalks are only designated as sidewalks in the walk-level network. Theoretically, aggregating spatial datasets from two levels is feasible, allowing multiple road types for a single segment. However, due to the accuracy of GPS point data, we cannot reliably determine e-scooter users’ choice of different road types on the same segment through map matching algorithms. Therefore, we opt not to do such aggregation. In this case, the map-matched trajectories are correct at the segment level, but the road type choice leans towards pedestrian infrastructure. Selecting the correct network is crucial for subsequent modeling, and the above discussion confirms its overall rationality.

Using the selected valid trip trajectories and the walk-level network, we performed map matching (FMM), assigning each trip a unique ID. The output included the trip ID, the sequence of traversed links and nodes, and the corresponding geometries matched to the road network. We manually verified a subset of randomly sampled routes by comparing

the map-matched paths to the original GPS trajectories. This examination revealed no significant issues, indicating the robustness of the used approach.

3.2.2. Post-Map-Matching trip processing

To prepare inputs for the choice set generation algorithm, we conducted post-processing on the map-matching results. Trips containing duplicate nodes or links within a single trajectory—such as circular routes or back-and-forth movements—were excluded. These patterns often indicate non-purposeful or leisure travel rather than trips between distinct locations. In many such cases, the origin and destination are very close, resulting in unrealistically short alternative routes that do not reflect the user’s actual decision-making. Including these trips could compromise the validity of route choice modeling.

Additionally, we needed to ensure that the trips were suitable for input into the choice set generation. For example, in BFSLE, an OD pair is considered as two nodes. So, from the trajectory data, we extracted nodes and the first and last nodes are marked as the origin and destination, respectively. For a trip with n links, we can obtain $n - 1$ nodes. Therefore, $n - 1$ should be at least 2 to determine an OD pair for BFSLE input. For trips with $n = 3$, there is only one link between the OD pair, resulting in no alternative choice set. For trips with $n = 4$, the alternative choice set is still very small or non-existent. Hence, we retained trips with $n \geq 5$.

3.3. Street view imagery data acquisition and processing

Understanding travelers’ route choices requires not only network-based factors (e.g., travel time, distance) but also contextual information about the built and natural environment along the route. Traditional data sources often fail to capture the visual and experiential qualities of streetscapes that influence perception and behavior. To address this gap, recent advances in computer vision allow for the extraction of rich environmental features from Google Street View (GSV) images, enabling a more nuanced analysis of street-level attributes in route choice modeling.

We extracted street-level built and natural environment characteristics from GSV imagery using deep learning-based semantic segmentation. Images were processed using the Pyramid Scene Parsing Network (PSPNet), a state-of-the-art model that classifies each pixel into one of 150 categories based on the MIT Scene Parsing Benchmark and the ADE20K dataset. These categories include natural elements (e.g., tree, sky) and built environment features (e.g., building, wall, pole). We computed the proportion of each feature at the image level to quantify streetscape composition.

To ensure comprehensive spatial coverage, we used GSV images from across Washington, D.C., collected throughout 2019. Although the e-scooter data spans from February to July, the use of a full-year GSV dataset helps maintain temporal consistency while improving spatial completeness. The final dataset includes 10,854 unique image locations, each with associated latitude and longitude coordinates. These point-level GSV features were linked to the road network by assigning each feature set to the nearest network segment within a 50-meter radius. However, due to the sparse and uneven distribution of GSV points, only a subset of links could be enriched in this way. To improve attribute coverage, we created

50-meter buffers around each GSV point and retained only those trips where at least 95% of the route length falls within these buffers. This filtering step significantly reduced missing data and improved the reliability of environmental feature estimates along each route. As a result, 2,587 trips were selected and their origin–destination pairs extracted for use in generating alternative routes.

4. Methodology: the Route choice model

This section outlines the methodology used to model e-scooter route choice behavior. We begin by describing the process of generating realistic and diverse route alternatives using the BFSLE algorithm. We then introduce the Path Size Logit (PSL) model, which accounts for overlapping routes and is well-suited for analyzing route choice behavior. Finally, we detail the variables used in the model, including both traditional infrastructure attributes and streetscape features derived from imagery data.

4.1. Choice set generation

The generation of the choice set utilizes the BFSLE algorithm, originally developed by Rieser-Schüssler et al. (2013). This algorithm employs repeated calculations of the least-cost path and has previously been applied to modeling bicycle route choices. Its selection over other methods was primarily due to its computational efficiency, as noted by Halldórsdóttir et al. (2014), and its suitability for integration within an agent-based simulation framework. Initially, the algorithm determines the least-cost path for a specific origin-destination (OD) pair and includes this path in the choice set. Subsequently, it iteratively removes links from the identified path, creating a series of sub-networks, provided OD connectivity and path uniqueness are maintained. These steps are repeated for each new sub-network until either the desired number of alternative paths is generated or no additional valid paths are identified. Whenever a new, unique path is discovered within a sub-network, it is added to the choice set. This iterative process constructs a tree structure composed of various sub-networks, with the depth of the tree representing the number of links removed from the initial network. The choice set is ultimately compiled using a breadth-first search approach, processing all sub-networks at the same level of depth before removing further links.

The main drawback of the BFSLE algorithm is that the generated choice set often comprises very similar routes, with most routes deviating only slightly from the least-cost path. This issue is less problematic when link density is low (e.g., in driving route choice), but it becomes particularly severe when the underlying network is dense. Therefore, to ensure greater heterogeneity among alternatives, we combined the BFSLE algorithm with a link penalization method. Tahlyan and Pinjari (2020) described a similar approach where routes are only added to the choice set if they differ by at least 5% from all previously generated routes. However, this method has a much higher computational cost. We ultimately chose a threshold = 0.9, only trips with multiple unique alternatives meeting this overlap threshold were included in further analysis. These shares are comparable to those found in previous bicycle route choice studies (Ton et al., 2018). The final dataset for route choice modeling included 2276 OD pairs along with their independent choice sets, averaging 5.5 alternative routes per trip.

4.2. Path size logit model

The multinomial logit (MNL) model is a method used to model the relationship between a multilevel dependent variable and a set of independent variables (Ben-Akiva and Lerman, 1985). In other words, given a set of explanatory variables, the MNL model can predict the probability of alternative outcomes for a multimodal response variable. However, MNL is unsuitable for route choice modeling with overlapping routes because it assumes that cyclists perceive each route as an independent alternative (Bekhor et al., 2006; Prato, 2009). To account for overlapping routes, the path size logit (PSL) model incorporates a correction factor (the path size attribute) into the route utility within the MNL framework. Thus, the PSL model is appropriate for studying factors influencing route choice behavior and is the most commonly used model in bicycle route choice research (Halldórsdóttir et al., 2014; Lukawska et al., 2023; Meister et al., 2023, 2024; Scott et al., 2021; Ton et al., 2018).

To calculate the path size term (PS_i) for route i , we use the following formula:

$$PS_i = \sum_{a \in i} \frac{L_a}{L_i} \frac{1}{\sum_{j \in C} \delta_{aj}} \quad (1)$$

where L_a is the length of link a , L_i is the length of route i , δ_{aj} is an indicator function that equals 1 if link a is in route j and 0 otherwise, and C is the choice set of all routes.

The utility (U_i) for route i in the Path Size Logit (PSL) model is given by:

$$U_i = \beta X_i + \ln(PS_i) \quad (2)$$

where U_i is the utility of route i , β is a vector of estimated coefficients, X_i is a vector of observed attributes for route i , and PS_i is the path size term for route i .

The probability (P_i) of choosing route i is then given by the standard multinomial logit formula:

$$P_i = \frac{e^{U_i}}{\sum_{j \in C} e^{U_j}} \quad (3)$$

where P_i is the probability of choosing route i and C is the choice set of all routes.

These equations together form the basis of the Path Size Logit model, which accounts for route overlap by incorporating the path size term into the utility calculation, thereby providing a more accurate representation of route choice behavior.

Figure 2: Illustration of roadway characterization and bicycle facility types: (1) major roads, (2) minor roads, (3) protected lanes, (4) painted lanes, (5) shared lanes. Source: OpenStreetMap (OSM), Google street view, District Department of Transportation (DDOT).

4.3. Variables included in e-scooter route choice model

To identify the factors that may influence e-scooter users' route choices, we generated attributes for all routes within the choice set. We have considered four categories of variables: trip characteristics, elevation, road type, and streetscape features, Table 1 provides detailed information about these variables. Figure 2 illustrates representative roadway and facility types.

Table 1: Variables considered in the e-scooter route choice model

Variable	Description
Trip characteristic	
Route length	Total length of all links in the route
Signals	Number of traffic signals along the route
Elevation	
Slope 2%-6%	Total length of links with a positive 2%-6% slope
Slope 6%-10%	Total length of links with a positive 6%-10% slope
Slope >10%	Total length of links with a positive >10% slope
Road type	
Bike paths	Total length of links with OSM tag highway="cycleway"
Sidewalks	Total length of links with OSM tag highway='footway'
Pedestrian zones	Total length of links with OSM tag highway="pedestrian"
Stairs	Total length of links with OSM tag highway="steps"
Service	Total length of links with OSM tag highway="service"
Major ^a w/ protected	Length of major roads with protected bike lanes OSM tag: cycleway={"track", "separate"}
Major ^a w/ painted	Length of major roads with painted bike lanes OSM tag: cycleway={"lane", "opposite_lane"}
Major ^a w/ shared	Length of major roads with shared bicycle markings OSM tag: cycleway={"shared_lane", "share_busway"}
Minor ^b w/ designated ^c	Length of minor roads with painted bike lanes OSM tag: cycleway={"lane", "opposite_lane", "track", "separate"}
Minor ^b w/ shared	Length of minor roads with shared bicycle markings OSM tag: cycleway={"shared_lane", "share_busway"}
Residential	Total length of links with OSM tag highway="residential"
Streetscape feature	
Tree	Length-weighted average of tree pixel proportion along the route
Tree×Summer	Interaction term between the tree index and the month, where months are coded as February to April = 0 and May to July = 1
Wall	Length-weighted average of wall pixel proportion along the route
Sky	Length-weighted average of sky pixel proportion along the route
Building	Length-weighted average of building pixel proportion along the route
Pole	Length-weighted average of pole pixel proportion along the route
Path size	Path size term

^a "Major" refers to roads tagged in OSM as highway={"primary", "secondary", "tertiary", "unclassified"} that have at least two car lanes in at least one direction.

^b "Minor" refers to roads tagged in OSM as highway={"primary", "secondary", "tertiary", "unclassified"} that have at most one car lane per direction.

^c "Designated" refers to protected and painted bike lanes, which are combined because protected lanes were scarce on minor roads.

Streetscape features were derived from the nearest available GSV points and aggregated at the route level using a weighted average based on link length. All elevation and road type variables were measured in kilometers. Elevation attributes were computed using 2' contour elevation data from Open Data DC. We estimated slope by extracting the closest elevation points to the origin and destination of each segment and dividing the elevation difference by segment length. Based on prior literature, slopes were categorized into ranges: 2%–6%, 6%–10%, and greater than 10%. For road type variables, we summed the lengths of links tagged with specific infrastructure types in OSM.

In the literature on micromobility and bicycle route choice, two broad strategies for representing road type are commonly observed. The first is based on the original OSM tags, where routes are characterized by the functional class of the underlying roadway (e.g., primary, secondary, tertiary, residential). This approach is straightforward and consistent with conventional practices in transportation planning. However, a drawback is that the associated length variables only proxy exposure to a given road class, rather than the actual distance traveled on such facilities. In the context of e-scooter travel, this distinction matters: categories such as off-street bike paths, service roads, or pedestrian zones have relatively clear behavioral interpretations, as they represent specific and consistent environments. By contrast, broad functional classes such as primary, secondary, or tertiary roads cover diverse conditions and designs, making it difficult to isolate the role of infrastructure within them. On these roads, cycling infrastructure is typically an inherent part of the main roadway and is represented in OSM by adding a "cycleway=*" tag to the existing "highway=*". For example, a segment tagged as "highway=primary" with "cycleway=separate" denotes a primary road with protected bike lanes. Building on prior work, we transformed road-type classifications into an infrastructure-focused specification by exploiting such combinations (Łukawska et al., 2023). This approach emphasizes specific design elements, such as protected, painted, or shared bike lanes, and addresses interpretive limitations by enabling examination of how detailed street-level infrastructure influences traveler behavior.

Two additional points merit clarification. First, the "highway=cycleway" tag explicitly indicates a separate path intended for cyclists and therefore corresponds to an off-street bicycle path (OpenStreetMap, 2025), distinct from bike lanes that are inherent to the roadway. Second, because sidewalks are represented in OSM as independent geometries that often run parallel and close to the main roadway, GPS errors may occasionally cause map-matching algorithms to misclassify movements on roadside bike lanes as trips on adjacent sidewalks, which may lead to a slight overestimation of sidewalk use.

5. Results

5.1. Descriptive statistics for chosen vs. alternative routes

We first compared the attribute values of the selected routes and those of the non-chosen alternatives to 1) help form hypothesis of the direction of impacts; 2) verify the validity of choice set generation results. Table 2 presents the mean and variance of each route attribute. It was observed that the mean length of the selected routes is greater. This is expected

because the choice set comprises the shortest path and slightly deviated second shortest paths. In fact, we found that approximately 20% of trips chose the shortest path.

To reflect the preference for elevation and road type relative to the shortest paths, we normalized the total length of both sets to 100% and then calculated the proportion of distance-based variables. We found that the proportions for slope 2%-6%, bike paths, sidewalks, residential roads, major roads with protected bike lanes, and median roads with designated bike lanes were positive, suggesting a positive effect. Conversely, the proportions for major roads with shared lanes, stairs, and service road types and for slope >10% were negative, indicating a potential negative effect. Streetscape-related statistics are similar between selected and alternative routes. However, this does not necessarily imply that these factors have no influence on route choice decisions; their effects will be further examined in the route choice model.

Table 2: Comparison of attribute values of the selected routes and non-chosen alternatives

Groups	Selected routes		Alternative routes		
	Mean (Std.)	Proportion	Mean (Std.)	Proportion	Proportion Diff.
Route length	903 (271)	100.00%	915 (268)	100.00%	0.00%
Signals	3 (2)	/	3 (2)	/	/
Slope 2%-6%	149 (120)	16.45%	149 (120)	16.33%	0.12%
Slope 6%-10%	66 (78)	7.35%	66 (78)	7.26%	0.10%
Slope >10%	77 (105)	8.49%	80 (108)	8.75%	-0.26%
Bike paths	188 (294)	20.85%	173 (279)	18.90%	1.95%
Sidewalks	413 (292)	45.70%	403 (285)	44.03%	1.67%
Pedestrian zones	1 (11)	0.14%	1 (10)	0.11%	0.02%
Stairs	1 (9)	0.09%	3 (19)	0.32%	-0.23%
Service	14 (43)	1.56%	23 (59)	2.47%	-0.92%
Major w/ protected	60 (147)	6.61%	57 (146)	6.27%	0.34%
Major w/ painted	18 (70)	1.99%	20 (72)	2.19%	-0.21%
Major w/ shared	12 (63)	1.35%	14 (71)	1.57%	-0.22%
Minor w/ designated	95 (175)	10.57%	91 (174)	9.93%	0.64%
Minor w/ shared	11 (51)	1.17%	10 (50)	1.13%	0.04%
Residential	74 (168)	8.23%	66 (147)	7.17%	1.06%
Tree	17% (8%)	/	17% (8%)	/	/
Wall	1% (3%)	/	1% (3%)	/	/
Sky	18% (6%)	/	18% (6%)	/	/
Building	18% (9%)	/	18% (9%)	/	/
Pole	0% (0%)	/	0% (0%)	/	/

5.2. Model outputs

The final model’s Concordance Index (C-index) was 0.72. The C-index, ranging from 0 to 1, assesses the performance of predictive classification models, with values above 0.5 indicating better than random guessing. A C-index of 0.72 in route choice modeling suggests that the model performs well in ranking the actual chosen route against alternative routes, indicating high predictive ability. Therefore, we believe this model effectively reflects users’ real preferences when facing different route choices. Table 3 presents the model estimates, with significance levels indicated for the variables. The positive estimate for the path size term is reasonable and consistent with findings from literature using BFSLE-based PSL (Meister et al., 2024), due to the significant overlap within the BFSLE-generated choice set.

In this PSL model, we found that the probability of choosing a route is negatively and highly significantly correlated with route length, indicating that e-scooter users tend to prefer shorter routes when other variables are held constant. Most existing bicycle/e-scooter route choice models also find a negative correlation between length and route utility (Halldórsdóttir et al., 2014; Lukawska et al., 2023; Meister et al., 2023, 2024; Scott et al., 2021; Ton et al., 2018). In Table 4, we sum the estimates of Route Length with other distance-based variables representing different road attributes to obtain the total effect of these attributes. We found that all total effects were negative. This means that although certain road attributes have positive impacts, the increased travel distance leads to an overall negative effect. This finding is reasonable and validates the model’s accuracy. As we filtered out recreational trips to ensure that most trips were related to daily travel needs, such as commuting and shopping, this negative effect underscores the decisive role of travel distance in shaping users’ route choice.

We found that e-scooter route choice is not sensitive to signal variables, which is somewhat unexpected. Although the high maneuverability and flexibility of e-scooters allow riders to bypass traffic signals or choose routes unaffected by signals, e-scooter users may prioritize route directness and convenience while riding, thus not deliberately avoiding signalized intersections. This could lead to the insignificance of signal variables in route choice. Additionally, differences in model applicability and dataset characteristics might also contribute to this discrepancy. In Meister et al. (2024)’s comparative study on bicycle route choice, the signal variable in their BFSLE-based PSL model yielded a positive estimate, whereas they obtained a negative estimate using a recursive logit model, a link-based rather than route-based Markov method. Applying a recursive logit model, Zhang et al. (2021) also found the number of traffic signals to be insignificant.

In terms of slope, the gradient of 2%-6% has a positive estimate that is marginally significant (p-value=0.1). The estimates for other slopes are not significant. This finding contrasts with most bicycle route choice models, where the slope coefficient typically becomes more negative as the gradient increases. However, Meister et al. (2023)’s findings about e-bicycle preference on slopes are very close to our results. They indicated that The average positive slope is higher for e-bicycles than bicycles and e-bicycles compensate a substantial share of the negative perception of grades. Besides, Zhang et al. (2021) found that e-scooter users are not sensitive to road slopes, which aligns with our finding that the estimates for slopes greater than 10% are not significant. The difference to normal bicycles can be

understood as e-scooters being driven by electric motors, so users do not deliberately avoid uphill routes. The positive effect for slopes between 2%-6% may reflect the flexibility of e-scooter users in route selection. Additionally, we tested an alternative variable representing the variance in elevation change, which also showed a positive effect. This indicates that e-scooter users might prefer routes with certain attributes rather than simply avoiding flat areas (Scott et al., 2021). Overall, these results suggest that e-scooter users are less constrained by slope when choosing routes and consider other factors more heavily. This contrasts with traditional bicycle route choice models and highlights the unique characteristics of e-scooters in urban transportation.

Table 3: E-scooter route choice model results

Variable	Coef.	Std. Err.	z-test
Trip characteristic			
Route length	-4.75***	0.58	-8.12
Signals	0.03	0.03	0.98
Elevation			
Slope 2%-6%	0.13	0.57	0.24
Slope 6%-10%	1.43.	0.87	1.65
Slope >10%	0.33	1.13	0.29
Road type			
Bike paths	0.51*	0.23	2.17
Sidewalks	0.48*	0.23	2.12
Pedestrian zones	6.78.	3.76	1.80
Stairs	-22.08***	5.03	-4.39
Service	-4.37***	0.80	-5.43
Major w/ protected	0.78*	0.34	2.31
Major w/ painted	-0.12	0.60	-0.20
Major w/ shared	0.57	0.68	0.84
Minor w/ designated	1.19***	0.29	4.10
Minor w/ shared	0.66	0.90	0.73
Residential	1.21***	0.32	3.71
Streetscape feature			
Tree	7.75*	3.10	2.50
Tree×Summer	20.03*	9.89	2.02
Wall	10.48**	3.34	3.13
Sky	5.77.	3.42	1.69
Building	7.73**	2.82	2.74
Pole	-369.03*	158.03	-2.34
Path Size	2.35***	0.09	26.17

Note: *** p < 0.001, ** p < 0.01, * p < 0.05, . p < 0.1

We found that e-scooter users may prefer using sidewalks and riding in pedestrian zones. As previously mentioned, e-scooter riding on sidewalks is permitted in Washington D.C. under certain circumstances. Additionally, our model tends to favor sidewalks given the network used in the FMM process. Despite this, the preference still raises concerns about pedestrian safety, since sidewalks are primarily intended for pedestrians rather than fast-moving vehicles. Such behavior may also violate local regulations, creating issues of legality. Therefore, urban planners and policymakers need to balance the convenience of e-scooters with pedestrian safety considerations and consider potential infrastructure adjustments. In addition, local road segments, such as residential streets, are favored by e-scooter users. This preference is likely due to their lower traffic volumes and average speeds, which make travel safer and more convenient for e-scooter riders. This finding aligns with existing literature, which shows that e-scooter usage is negatively correlated with posted speed limits (of Transportation , PBOT; Zhang et al., 2021). By contrast, stairs are typically an undesirable road feature for e-scooter riders, as they require carrying the device or attempting to ride in unsafe conditions. Consequently, the estimated coefficient for stairs is negative and significant. Similarly, service roads are associated with a negative effect, possibly due to restricted access in certain cases.

The estimation results also reveal heterogeneous effects across bicycle facility types (protected, painted, shared) and roadway contexts (major vs. minor roads). On major roads, protected lanes are positively and significantly associated with route choice, whereas painted lanes and shared markings are not significant. This suggests that in high-volume traffic environments, only protected facilities provide sufficient separation to influence e-scooter riders' choices. On minor roads, however, the combined category of designated lanes (protected and painted) is strongly significant¹. These results suggest that the utility gap between protected and painted facilities is context dependent: pronounced on major roads and minimal on minor roads. On major roads, only protected lanes generate meaningful utility gains, whereas on minor roads both types appear beneficial. This pattern is plausible given the lower traffic intensity and narrower cross-sections of minor roads, where even painted lanes may provide enough comfort to be valued by riders. By contrast, shared lanes consistently show no significant influence on e-scooter route choice across road contexts, suggesting a limited role in promoting e-scooter usage.

Furthermore, we examined the influence of various streetscape features, including tree coverage, seasonal effects, sky visibility, buildings, walls, and poles. The results indicate that the presence of trees along a route positively impacts e-scooter route choice. This suggests that routes lined with trees may be preferred due to their aesthetic appeal, shading, and potential cooling effects, which improve overall riding comfort. Moreover, this effect is further amplified during summer months, as indicated by the interaction between tree coverage and heat exposure. The stronger preference for tree-covered routes in the summer is intuitive, as shade can provide relief from heat, making the riding experience more comfortable. This finding

¹Protected lanes on minor roads were relatively scarce, leading to larger standard errors and marginal significance when we separated protected lanes and painted lanes on minor roads into two variables. Hence, the two types of bicycle facility were combined into a single variable, i.e., minor roads with “designated” bike lane.

highlights the importance of urban greenery in promoting micromobility use, particularly in regions with hot climates. Sky visibility also appears to influence route choice, though its effect is less pronounced. Open-sky routes may provide a sense of openness and a more visually appealing riding environment. We found that built environment features also play a role in shaping route preferences. The results show that routes with walls and buildings along them are more likely to be chosen by e-scooter users. One possible explanation is that such routes provide a sense of enclosure, separating riders from vehicle traffic and creating a more protected environment. Additionally, these routes are mostly present in commercial or mixed-use areas where e-scooter riders frequently travel for commuting, shopping, or other activities. On the other hand, the presence of poles along a route is strongly negatively associated with e-scooter route choice. This may be because poles often indicate physical obstructions on sidewalks or shared-use paths, which can interfere with the maneuverability and flow of e-scooter travel.

In addition, several other streetscape variables were also tested in the model but consistently showed no significant effects. For instance, plant and grass did not influence route choice, suggesting that not all greenery matters equally: what riders value is not the mere presence of vegetation but the functional benefits of tree canopy, such as shade and enclosure. Similarly, variables such as road and car represent basic roadway elements that are ubiquitous across the network, and thus provide little explanatory power for differentiating route preferences.

5.3. Value-of-Distance indicators

In the context of route choice models, the Value of Distance (VoD) metrics are commonly calculated. These metrics represent the equivalent distance that would be traded off for a particular attribute along the route. For linear parameter models, VoDs are given by the ratio of parameter i to the length parameter. The table presents the marginal effects, total effects, and VoD indicators for various variables. VoDs above or below 0 are considered to increase or decrease the perceived length by the corresponding VoD ratio. It is important to note that the negative utility of distance cannot be fully offset by any single road attribute, and thus cannot make an overall positive contribution to utility.

The negative effects of certain route features on e-scooter travel are particularly pronounced for the *Stairs* variable. On routes with stairs, the length parameter decreases by 22.08, indicating that e-scooter riders are willing to travel 465% extra distance to avoid stairs. Similarly, the presence of service roads has a negative total effect of -4.37, with VoD indicators of 92%, respectively. This suggests that riders may have limited right-of-way on this type of roads, potentially leading to additional travel distance due to necessary detours. Conversely, several variables show reduced perceived length, indicating a willingness to take routes with certain features. For instance, major roads with protected bike lanes, median roads with designated bike lanes, and residential roads have total effects of -3.97, -3.56, and -3.54, with VoD indicators of -16%, -25%, and -25%, respectively, indicating that riders view these roads as safer and more continuous options.

Sidewalks and off-street bike paths reduce perceived distance by about 10–11%. Their effect is modest, likely because these facilities often involve slower speeds, pedestrian inter-

ruptions, and limited network continuity, making them less influential than on-road protected or designated lanes. Stairs and service roads are strong deterrents, pointing to the need for ramps, lifts, or alternative alignments to maintain accessibility. By contrast, protected lanes on major roads, designated lanes on minor roads, and residential streets (e.g., bicycle boulevards) provide the strongest utility gains, indicating that investments should prioritize safe and continuous on-street facilities across different traffic contexts. Sidewalks and off-street paths reduce perceived distance only modestly, so they should be treated as supplementary connectors for filling gaps in the network rather than as substitutes for dedicated on-street infrastructure.

Unlike road infrastructure variables, streetscape features such as tree coverage, buildings, and poles are measured as proportions (0%-100%) rather than absolute distances. Consequently, their VoD values represent the impact of a full transition from 0% to 100%, which is not directly comparable to the VoD of road attributes measured in kilometers. A more practical approach is to consider marginal changes. For instance, tree coverage has a VoD of -1.63, meaning that if tree coverage along a route increased from 0% to 100%, riders would perceive the route as 1.63 times shorter than its actual length. However, in practice, tree coverage is unlikely to change drastically from 0% to full coverage. If tree coverage increases by 1 percentage point, the corresponding reduction in perceived distance would be 1.63% in the spring. In the summer, where the interaction effect further amplifies this preference, the total perceived distance reduction for a 1 percentage point increase in tree coverage would be 5.85%. Similarly, poles exhibit the highest VoD value (77.73), indicating that if pole coverage increased from 0% to 100%, riders would perceive the route as 77.73 times longer. In a more realistic scenario, if pole coverage increases by just 1 percentage point, the perceived increase in route length would be 7.77%. This suggests that even a minor increase in pole density can significantly deter e-scooter riders.

We can illustrate the VoD values of streetscape features in a more intuitive way and compare them with road infrastructure effects. In the summer case, an absolute increase of 4.3% in tree coverage produces the same effect as residential roads (VoD=-0.25). Similarly, an absolute increase of 11.3% in wall, 15.4% in building, and 15.3% in spring tree coverage would yield comparable effects, while just an absolute decrease of 0.3% in pole has the same magnitude. Baseline levels are reported in Table 2, note that the potentially feasible scope of change differs across features. Importantly, reaching a 25% VoD reduction requires only the presence of residential streets, whereas environmental attributes demand much larger coverage changes to achieve comparable effects. As shown in Table 2, streetscape features exhibit little difference across routes, suggesting that their role is not to determine whether a path is chosen but rather to shape trade-offs within feasible options. Furthermore, although environmental context plays some role in shaping rider perceptions and their effects are statistically significant, their inclusion did not meaningfully improve model fit or predictive concordance. By contrast, road infrastructure exerts the primary influence on e-scooter route choice, as evidenced by the clear differences in descriptive statistics between chosen and alternative routes. In all, distance and infrastructure define the foundation of route selection, while streetscape features adjust comfort and attractiveness at the margin.

Finally, we note that Meister et al. (2024) found substantial variation in VoDs for bike

lanes across the three models they applied, even when using the same dataset. Both the magnitudes and the rankings of VoDs differed markedly by model. They also showed that the Recursive Logit (RL) model was generally less sensitive to route attributes than the BFSLE model, which may help explain why the VoD for stairs, despite being the most negative attribute, was only 55% in their estimates (Zhang et al., 2021), much lower than in our results. It should also be recognized that the underlying model remains linear, and the estimated coefficients are inevitably affected by multicollinearity. Taken together, these comparisons highlight that results can vary considerably across modeling approaches; policy decisions should therefore draw on multiple model specifications and consider both the sign and the relative ranking of VoDs when interpreting behavioral implications.

Table 4: Value-of-Distance indicators

Variable	Marginal Effect	Total Effect	VoD
Road type			
Residential	1.21	-3.54	-0.25
Minor w/ designated	1.19	-3.56	-0.25
Major w/ protected	0.78	-3.97	-0.16
Bike paths	0.51	-4.24	-0.11
Sidewalks	0.48	-4.26	-0.10
Service	-4.37	-9.12	0.92
Stairs	-22.08	-26.83	4.65
Streetscape feature			
Tree (summer)	27.78	23.03	-5.85
Wall	10.48	5.73	-2.21
Building	7.73	2.98	-1.63
Tree (spring)	7.75	3.01	-1.63
Pole	-369.03	-373.78	77.73

Note: Only variables with $p < 0.05$ are reported in this table.

6. Discussion

This study provides new insights into how roadway infrastructure and streetscape features shape e-scooter route choice in an urban setting. The results show that on major roads with heavy traffic and multiple lanes, only protected lanes significantly boost e-scooter usage, while on narrower, lower-volume minor roads (e.g., low-speed collectors), both protected and painted lanes encourage e-scooter riding. In other words, protected bicycle facilities are uniquely important on major roads, but the utility gap between protected and painted lanes appears less pronounced on minor roads. This pattern aligns with findings from bicycle route choice studies, which also show that on major roads only protected tracks

are effective, whereas painted lanes alone do not provide sufficient protection (Łukawska et al., 2023). The similarity suggests that e-scooter riders exhibit a comparable risk-aversion profile to cyclists in high-traffic contexts, where substantial separation from motor vehicles is necessary. On both major and minor roads, shared lane markings do not significantly encourage usage. However, residential streets with calmer traffic and lower volumes emerge as strongly preferred environments for e-scooter users. In these settings, shared lanes or even the absence of dedicated facilities are common, while protected lanes are relatively rare. Therefore, treatments such as bicycle boulevards, which are enhanced shared streets that incorporate traffic calming and management measures, are usually adequate to improve micromobility riding comfort in residential areas.

Our analysis also highlights the complementary role of streetscape features in shaping route preferences. This study is among the first to integrate high-resolution GSV-derived imagery into a PSL-based e-scooter route choice model, demonstrating the potential of combining computer vision with behavioral modeling to inform micromobility planning. Improvements in micro-scale environmental qualities, such as greenery or landscaping, can enhance the comfort and appeal of a route for e-scooter riders. Notably, our results suggest that e-scooter users value routes with greater tree coverage, especially in the summer when the tree shades can provide major relief from heat. Moreover, e-scooter users are more likely to choose routes with greater sky visibility and some degree of enclosure by buildings or walls, highlighting the role of urban design features (e.g., openness, enclosure) in shaping micromobility routing choices. On the other hand, plants and grass have no significant effect on route choice, suggesting that e-scooter riders value the functional benefits of vegetation (such as the shade provided by tree canopy) rather than its mere presence.

Finally, e-scooter users and cyclists share similar route choice patterns but with some notable differences. The central role of bicycle infrastructure in shaping e-scooter route choice mirrors patterns commonly observed among cyclists, reinforcing previously noted tendencies toward risk aversion: the higher the road class and traffic intensity, the more critical physical separation becomes. At the same time, e-scooter users exhibit greater flexibility in certain aspects. They show tolerance for, or even preference toward, routes with moderate elevation changes, likely due to the assistance provided by electric motors. A further distinction is that e-scooter route choice shows limited sensitivity to the number of traffic signals, unlike cyclists who are more affected by safety concerns and delays at intersections (Broach et al., 2012; Lu et al., 2018). This difference can be explained by two factors. First, e-scooter trips are generally shorter than bicycle trips (Cubells et al., 2023), and in our data most leisure trips have been filtered out, leaving primarily utilitarian trips that are even shorter in distance. For such trips, detouring to avoid signals is rarely worthwhile, since the added distance or time may outweigh the delay at intersections. Second, the electric motor reduces the physical cost of frequent stops, so waiting at signals imposes a smaller burden. As a result, riders emphasize directness and continuity when selecting their routes.

7. Conclusion

This study explored the factors influencing e-scooter route choice within the urban environment of Washington, D.C., by applying a Path Size Logit (PSL) model to a large-scale GPS trajectory dataset collected from shared e-scooters. We find clear preferences for on-street bicycle infrastructure: protected lanes on major roads and designated lanes on minor roads are associated with higher route utility, while shared markings are not. Residential streets are also favored, whereas stairs and service roads are strongly avoided.

In addition to traditional GIS-based infrastructure variables, our model incorporates environmental features extracted from Google Street View (GSV) imagery, allowing us to capture streetscape factors beyond the infrastructure network. This integration of streetscape-level data represents a novel contribution of the study. Tree coverage significantly enhances route attractiveness, especially in warmer months, while visual obstructions such as poles strongly deter route choice. Features like walls and buildings are also associated with higher utility, possibly due to the perceived structure, protection, or activity density in those areas. The Value of Distance (VoD) framework clarifies the behavioral trade-offs implied by the estimates. No attribute fully offsets the disutility of longer distance. The largest aversion is to stairs; service roads also increase perceived distance. By contrast, designated lanes on minor roads and residential streets show the strongest perceived-distance reductions, followed by protected lanes on major roads. Sidewalks and off-street paths reduce perceived distance only modestly. Although the direction of effects is consistent with prior studies, the relative importance differs, highlighting the need to consider context when interpreting VoD magnitudes.

These findings carry major policy implications. First, there is a clear need for prioritizing fully protected lanes on high-traffic corridors, as only separately bicycle facilities materially promote e-scooter usage on these roads. Meanwhile, on minor roads with less traffic and lower traffic, a painted lane appears to be as effective as a separated lane in attracting e-scooter riding, despite the less clear safety benefits it provides (DiGioia et al., 2017). Moreover, our results suggest that shared lane markings should be limited to residential streets rather than applied on larger, faster roads. In addition, our study highlights the complementary role of streetscape features (e.g., trees, sky visibility, and building facades) in promoting a route’s functional desirability and aesthetic appeal. Notably, to support and encourage micromobility use, cities should prioritize expanding tree canopy for summer shade and enhancing urban design elements that create a balance of openness and enclosure.

A key limitation of this study is that our model did not include demographic and socioeconomic variables due to data unavailability. Future research should investigate the heterogeneity of e-scooter user preferences by incorporating these variables. Future studies may also consider a broader range of infrastructure variables, such as specific sidewalk characteristics. Finally, our model was developed using data from the City of Washington DC. More studies from other land-use and transportation contexts are needed to verify the findings of this study on e-scooter route choice behavior.

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